

Artem BARATIUK,
Postgraduate Student, Assistant at the
Department of Psychodiagnostics and Clinical Psychology,
Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv
Email: bergmanartem@knu.ua
ORCID: [0000-0003-3473-0434](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3473-0434)

Assessment of the Effect of Presence and Immersion as Psychometric Constructs in Virtual Reality

Presence and immersion are key psychometric constructs in studies of human interaction with virtual environments. Although these concepts are often used interchangeably, they have substantial differences. Immersion is defined as an objective characteristic of the technological environment that determines the level of user involvement through visual, auditory, and tactile stimuli (Wilkinson et al., 2021). At the same time, presence is a subjective experience of the user that is expressed in the feeling of “actually being” in a virtual environment, regardless of its technical characteristics (Korżel and Lupkowski, 2023). Research confirms that although these two constructs are closely interrelated, an increase in the level of immersion does not always guarantee a rise in presence, because the latter is influenced by cognitive and emotional factors (Smith and Mulligan, 2021).

In addition to presence and immersion, research covers related concepts: engagement (the intensity of attention), social presence (the feeling of other people nearby), and embodiment (the feeling of “ownership” of a virtual body). These factors can strengthen or modulate the basic feeling of presence.

The psychological perception of virtual reality covers three aspects: the cognitive aspect (perception and decision making), the affective aspect (emotional engagement), and the sensory aspect (visual, auditory, and tactile stimuli). Their interaction determines the depth of immersion and the feeling of presence (Maneuvrier et al., 2021; Cadet and Chainay, 2020; Jung and Lindeman, 2021).

The interaction of these components (cognitive, affective, and sensory) with personal variables and physiological reactivity determines the quality of the virtual reality experience and the level of psychological adaptation of the user to an artificial environment.

The first models of presence (Witmer and Singer, 1998; Slater and Wilbur, 1997) defined it through the degree of attention to the virtual reality environment and a set of technological factors that provide immersion (the width of the field of view, interactivity, and so forth).

The assessment and measurement of the level of presence and immersion is critically important for several areas of research. In cognitive psychology, the study of these constructs makes it possible to analyze how a person perceives reality and makes decisions in altered conditions (Kim et al., 2021). In the field of user experience design, understanding the effect of presence helps to create more effective and user-friendly interfaces for virtual reality applications, providing better user interaction with digital environments (Abbey et al., 2021). In psychotherapy, immersive technologies are already used for the treatment of phobias, post-traumatic stress disorder, and emotional disorders, because they make it possible to create controlled environments for the gradual influence on the psycho-emotional state of patients (Takac et al., 2021).

Subjective methods for assessing the effect of presence and immersion in virtual reality are the most widespread due to their ease of use and ability directly to reflect the user’s experience. The most common subjective questionnaires are the Presence Questionnaire, the ITC-Sense of Presence Inventory, and the Slater-Usuh-Steed Questionnaire. They assess engagement, ecological plausibility, negative effects, and the comparison of the virtual reality experience with the real one. Although these

Note: This preprint is an English translation of the article originally published in Ukrainian:

Baratiuk, A. (2025). Otsiniuvannia efektu prysutnosti ta imersii yak psykhologichnykh konstruktiv u virtualnii realnosti [Assessment of the Effect of Presence and Immersion as Psychometric Constructs in Virtual Reality]. *Psychological Dimensions of Culture, Economy, and Management*, (28), 15–23. ISSN 2409-1375.

instruments are popular, researchers emphasize the need to adapt them to modern virtual reality technologies.

To increase the validity of assessments, researchers often:

- Combine questionnaires (Presence Questionnaire, ITC-Sense of Presence Inventory, Slater-Usuh-Steed Questionnaire) with short real-time self-assessments (for example, subjective scales that the user fills in during the stay in virtual reality rather than only “after the fact”).
- Apply “mixed” methods, in which the subjective assessment is compared with psychophysiological and behavioral indicators (Kim et al., 2021).

However, subjective methods have substantial limitations: the answers may depend on the individual characteristics of the user, his or her previous experience and expectations (Putrawangsa et al., 2023). In addition, the results of such assessments may vary depending on the context of the experiment, which complicates their reproducibility.

The assessment of the effect of presence and immersion in virtual reality often relies on subjective methods such as questionnaires and self-assessments. However, recent research demonstrates growing interest in objective psychophysiological methods that make it possible to analyze the neurological and physiological reactions of users in a virtual reality environment.

Objective psychophysiological methods include electroencephalography, functional magnetic resonance imaging, heart rate variability, and eye tracking. They record brain activity, changes in heart rhythm, and eye movements that correlate with the level of immersion and presence. For example, increased activation in the frontal areas or changes in the pupils may indicate increased attention to virtual stimuli (Dey et al., 2020; Schöne et al., 2023). At the same time, it is worth remembering ethical and methodological issues, in particular the storage and anonymization of biological and neurological data of research participants.

Objective behavioral and experimental approaches to assessing the effect of presence and immersion in virtual reality are based on the analysis of user movements, reactions to external stimuli, as well as spatial orientation and the ability to learn in a virtual reality environment. In contrast to subjective methods of assessment, these approaches make it possible to obtain direct data about the behavior of users without the need for a survey, which minimizes cognitive biases and variability of responses.

One of the key methods for assessing the level of immersion is the analysis of body movements and positional changes during the virtual reality experience. Studies have found that users who feel a high level of presence demonstrate more natural movements, in particular head tilts, changes in body position, and adaptation to the virtual environment (Abbey et al., 2021). An important aspect is the study of the user’s reactions when interacting with objects in virtual reality: the more realistically they are perceived, the more accurately and quickly motor actions are performed (Domínguez et al., 2020). The use of motion tracking makes it possible to analyze how naturally a person moves in virtual reality, which is an indicator of a high level of immersion.

Another indicator of presence is the reaction to unexpected events (the startle response), which is used to assess the level of user engagement in virtual reality. Studies have shown that users who demonstrate a high level of immersion have an enhanced physiological reaction to unexpected auditory and visual stimuli, such as sharp sounds or sudden changes in the virtual environment (Savalle et al., 2024). This reaction is confirmed by experiments in which the analysis of electroencephalographic activity showed a significant increase in the P300 amplitude in response to unexpected stimuli during the virtual reality experience, which indicates the activation of cognitive processing of stimuli and an increase in the level of presence (Genz et al., 2024).

Studies of spatial navigation and motor learning in virtual reality make it possible to assess how well a user is able to navigate and adapt to a virtual environment. The results of experimental studies show that the higher the level of immersion, the more effectively users remember spatial routes and adapt to the surrounding environment (Kaplan-Rakowski and Gruber, 2023). Spatial learning in virtual reality also makes it possible to model the influence of the virtual environment on the cognitive functions of users, which is especially useful for training skills such as driving or controlling complex technical processes (Rao et al., 2024).

Note: This preprint is an English translation of the article originally published in Ukrainian.

A final important approach to assessing presence is the comparison of real and virtual experience by means of methods of simulation recognition. Research shows that users who experience a high level of presence in virtual reality distinguish real and virtual memories less accurately after the experiment has ended (Smith and Mulligan, 2021). Thus, the high quality of the immersive experience can cause a cognitive “merging” of real and virtual experience. The analysis of experimental data also shows that some types of virtual reality scenarios, in particular those that simulate real physical spaces, can create a false memory effect, which is particularly important for research in the field of cognitive psychology (Wilkinson et al., 2021).

Conclusions.

The field of assessing presence and immersion in virtual reality is currently quite developed and relies on a wide range of subjective and objective methods. At the same time, there remain a number of gaps, in particular the insufficient consistency of existing questionnaires, the complexity of interpreting psychophysiological indicators, and the variability of behavioral reactions.

Promising directions for further research appear to be:

- The development of hybrid (“mixed”) instruments that combine subjective questionnaires with objective physiological and behavioral indicators.
- The standardization of protocols for conducting virtual reality experiments (the control of the influence of novelty, cybersickness, and external distractions).
- The consideration of users’ personal characteristics for constructing individualized models of presence (for example, cognitive styles, the propensity for immersion, previous experience).
- Multi-user environments and the study of social presence, which open new challenges in assessment (co-presence, social dynamics, and so forth).

Overall, the improvement of psychometric instruments and methods that take into account cognitive and emotional factors is a necessary condition for ensuring accurate and reliable measurement of the effect of presence and immersion in virtual reality.

References:

- Abbey, A., Porssut, T., Herbelin, B., & Boulic, R. (2021). Assessing the Impact of Mixed Reality Immersion on Presence and Embodiment. *Proceedings of the 14th ACM SIGGRAPH Conference on Motion, Interaction and Games*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3487983.3488304>.
- Cadet, L., & Chainay, H. (2020). Memory of virtual experiences: Role of immersion, emotion and sense of presence. *Int. J. Hum. Comput. Stud.*, 144, 102506. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2020.102506>.
- Dey, A., Phoon, J., Saha, S., Dobbins, C., & Billingham, M. (2020). A Neurophysiological Approach for Measuring Presence in Immersive Virtual Environments. *2020 IEEE International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality (ISMAR)*, 474-485. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISMAR50242.2020.00072>.
- Domínguez, J., De Juan Ripoll, C., Contero, M., & Alcañiz, M. (2020). I walk, therefore I am: a multidimensional study on the influence of the locomotion method upon presence in virtual reality. *J. Comput. Des. Eng.*, 7, 577-590. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jcde/qwaa040>.
- Genz, F., Dreer, F., Krötz, F., D’Amelio, M., & Kranzlmüller, D. (2024). Measuring the Influence of Alcohol Consumption on Presence in Virtual Reality. *Computer Science Research Notes*. <https://doi.org/10.24132/csrn.3401.19>.
- Jeong, W., & Oh, S. (2020). Correlation between the immersion and presence: focused on virtual reality contents. *2020 International Conference on Information and Communication Technology Convergence (ICTC)*, 474-477. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICTC49870.2020.9289207>.
- Jung, S., & Lindeman, R. (2021). Perspective: Does Realism Improve Presence in VR? Suggesting a Model and Metric for VR Experience Evaluation. , 2. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frvir.2021.693327>.

- Kaplan-Rakowski, R., & Gruber, A. (2023). An experimental study on reading in high-immersion virtual reality. *Br. J. Educ. Technol.*, 55, 541-559. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.13392>.
- Kim, S., Laine, T., & Suk, H. (2021). Presence Effects in Virtual Reality Based on User Characteristics: Attention, Enjoyment, and Memory. *Electronics*, 10, 1051. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ELECTRONICS10091051>.
- Korżel, K., & Lupkowski, P. (2023). The Phenomenon of Presence in Virtual Reality Is Mistakenly Equated with Immersion. *PRESENCE: Virtual and Augmented Reality*, 32, 117-127. https://doi.org/10.1162/pres_a_00404.
- Maneuvrier, A., Decker, L., Renaud, P., Ceyte, G., & Ceyte, H. (2021). Field (In)dependence Flexibility Following a Virtual Immersion Is Associated With Cybersickness and Sense of Presence. , 2. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frvir.2021.706712>.
- Putrawangsa, D., Theresia, C., Yogasara, T., & Theopilus, Y. (2023). The Effect of Sex Differences and Experience of Using Virtual Reality on Presence. *Jurnal Optimasi Sistem Industri*. <https://doi.org/10.25077/josi.v22.n1.p61-68.2023>.
- Rao, A., Bhavsar, A., Chowdhury, S., Chandra, S., Negi, R., Duraisamy, P., & Dutt, V. (2024). Evaluating the efficacy of a haptic feedback, 360° treadmill-integrated virtual reality framework and longitudinal training on decision-making performance in a complex search-and-shoot simulation. , 13051, 130510C - 130510C-13. <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.3017333>.
- Savalle, E., Pillette, L., Won, K., Argelaguet, F., Lécuyer, A., & Macé, M. (2024). Towards electrophysiological measurement of presence in virtual reality through auditory oddball stimuli.. *Journal of neural engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1741-2552/ad5cc2>.
- Schöne, B., Kisker, J., Lange, L., Gruber, T., Sylvester, S., & Osinsky, R. (2023). The reality of virtual reality. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1093014>.
- Slater, M. (1999). Measuring Presence: A Response to the Witmer and Singer Presence Questionnaire. *Presence*, 8, 560-565. <https://doi.org/10.1162/105474699566477>.
- Smith, S., & Mulligan, N. (2021). Immersion, presence, and episodic memory in virtual reality environments. *Memory*, 29, 983 - 1005. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09658211.2021.1953535>.
- Takac, M., Collett, J., Conduit, R., & Foe, A. (2021). A cognitive model for emotional regulation in virtual reality exposure. *Virtual Reality*, 27, 159-172. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10055-021-00531-4>.
- Wilkinson, M., Brantley, S., & Feng, J. (2021). A Mini Review of Presence and Immersion in Virtual Reality. *Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting*, 65, 1099 - 1103. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1071181321651148>.